

Artifact Evaluation Guide

This document explains how to reproduce the figures and tables used in the experimental part of the paper. First, unzip the artifact package:

```
unzip ase26-study.zip
```

This document provides two workflows for artifact evaluation:

- **Mode A: Reproduce from the provided study data.** Use the already committed processed data and regenerate the paper-facing figures and tables only. Read **Tested Environment**, **Prerequisites**, **Quick Start**, and **Artifact Order**.
- **Mode B: Rebuild the study from scratch.** Recreate the OpenClaw study preconditions, rerun the analysis scripts, and then regenerate the paper-facing artifacts. Read **Tested Environment**, **Prerequisites**, **OpenClaw Source Verification**, **Rebuilding the Study from Scratch**, and finally **Artifact Order**.

The current paper result section is in:

- [docs/reports/result.tex](#)

The artifact outputs are written to:

- [docs/reports/artifact_eval](#)

Tested Environment

This artifact package was prepared and checked in the following environment:

- OS: Linux
- Shell: `bash`
- Python: `python3`
- Git: available in `PATH`
- `rg` (ripgrep): available in `PATH`

The artifact-generation scripts are pure Python and can regenerate the paper-facing outputs from committed processed data. The repository also keeps the additional scripts and study inputs needed to rerun the experiments from scratch.

Prerequisites

Before running the artifact workflow, make sure that:

- `python3` is installed and available in `PATH`

- `pip` is available for that Python installation
- `git` is available in `PATH`
- `rg` is available in `PATH`
- the working directory is the repository root
- the repository keeps the committed processed inputs under `data/processed/`
- the repository keeps the curated CVE labels under `data/raw/openclaw_cves_full_source_single_label.csv`

Install the Python plotting dependencies:

```
python3 -m pip install -r requirements-artifact.txt
```

Expected Directory Layout

The minimum package expected by this guide contains:

- `ARTIFACT_EVALUATION.md`
- `requirements-artifact.txt`
- `scripts/`
- `data/processed/`
- `data/raw/openclaw_cves_full_source_single_label.csv`
- `docs/reports/artifact_eval/`
- `patches/openclaw/0001-runtime-instrumentation.patch`
- `openclaw/`

The guide assumes you run all commands from the repository root.

OpenClaw Source Verification

This package already includes an `openclaw/` source tree. Before downloading a fresh copy, check whether the bundled tree is already the expected baseline and whether the runtime-instrumentation hooks are present.

Expected baseline commit:

- `36cf8ca472a85aff759bdf3a26db927c050588a0`

Recommended checks:

```
git -C openclaw rev-parse HEAD
rg -n "recordInputSurface(Segment|ExecutionEvent|ModelCall)|tool_use_observed|memory_flush_tr
```

If the commit matches and the instrumentation markers are present, reuse the local `openclaw/` directory and do not download anything.

If the directory is missing, at a different baseline, or lacks the expected instrumentation markers, clone and patch it as follows:

```
git clone https://github.com/openclaw/openclaw.git
git -C openclaw checkout 36cf8ca472a85aff759bdf3a26db927c050588a0
git -C openclaw apply ../patches/openclaw/0001-runtime-instrumentation.patch
```

The patch used by the study is included at:

- `patches/openclaw/0001-runtime-instrumentation.patch`

Quick Start

Then run:

```
python3 scripts/generate_artifact_outputs.py
```

This command regenerates the paper-facing tables and figures and writes them to `docs/reports/artifact_eval`.

Rebuilding the Study from Scratch

This section applies only if you want to rerun the study pipeline instead of reusing the committed processed data.

Additional prerequisites for a full rerun

- Node.js and `npm` available in `PATH`
- the OpenClaw source tree available under `openclaw/`
- model and provider credentials placed in `secrets/local.env` or in the shell environment, depending on the runner
- web-search-enabled runs additionally require `BRAVE_API_KEY`

RQ1: External input surfaces and taint paths

Run:

```
node scripts/analyze_external_inputs_taint.js
python3 scripts/generate_external_input_surface_taxonomy.py
python3 scripts/generate_input_surface_sink_matrix.py
python3 scripts/generate_input_surface_sink_paths.py
```

This regenerates the taint-analysis outputs and the surface/sink summaries used by Table 1 and Table 2.

RQ2: Runtime contribution

Run the regular benchmark:

```
RQ2_MODEL_REF='modelstudio/qwen3.5-plus' RQ2_MODEL_LABEL='modelstudio_qwen3.5-plus' RQ2_DISABLE_TIM
RQ2_MODEL_REF='google/gemini-3-flash' RQ2_MODEL_LABEL='google_gemini-3-flash' RQ2_DISABLE_TIM
RQ2_MODEL_REF='modelstudio/glm-5' RQ2_MODEL_LABEL='modelstudio_glm-5' RQ2_DISABLE_TIMEOUT=1 n
RQ2_MODEL_REF='modelstudio/kimi-k2.5' RQ2_MODEL_LABEL='modelstudio_kimi-k2.5' RQ2_DISABLE_TIM
```

Run the special tasks:

```
RQ2_MODEL_REF='modelstudio/qwen3.5-plus' RQ2_MODEL_LABEL='modelstudio_qwen3.5-plus' RQ2_DISABLE_TIM
RQ2_MODEL_REF='google/gemini-3-flash' RQ2_MODEL_LABEL='google_gemini-3-flash' RQ2_DISABLE_TIM
RQ2_MODEL_REF='modelstudio/glm-5' RQ2_MODEL_LABEL='modelstudio_glm-5' RQ2_DISABLE_TIMEOUT=1 n
RQ2_MODEL_REF='modelstudio/kimi-k2.5' RQ2_MODEL_LABEL='modelstudio_kimi-k2.5' RQ2_DISABLE_TIM
```

Aggregate the runtime phase summaries:

```
python3 scripts/summarize_runtime_phase_contributions.py --regular-dir data/processed/runtime
python3 scripts/summarize_runtime_phase_contributions.py --regular-dir data/processed/runtime
python3 scripts/summarize_runtime_phase_contributions.py --regular-dir data/processed/runtime
python3 scripts/summarize_runtime_phase_contributions.py --regular-dir data/processed/runtime
```

These outputs are used by Table 3, Figure 1, and Table 4.

RQ3: bug-related risk on taint paths

Run:

```
python3 scripts/analyze_input_surface_path_updates.py
python3 scripts/alberg_diagram.py
```

This regenerates the bug/update concentration analysis used by Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Expected Outputs

After a successful run, the following outputs should exist:

- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_1_external_input_surface_taxonomy.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_2_input_surface_sink_matrix.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_3_prompt_contribution.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_4_execution_control.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_5_cves_and_protections.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/figure_1_qwen_prompt_share_stacked.pdf
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/figure_2_alberg_bugfix.pdf
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/figure_3_alberg_update.pdf

You can validate the output directory with:

```
find docs/reports/artifact_eval -maxdepth 1 -type f | sort
```

Artifact Order

The scripts generate the artifacts in the same order used by the paper.

Table 1: External Input-Surface Taxonomy

Outputs:

- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_1_external_input_surface_taxonomy.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_1_external_input_surface_taxonomy.csv

Primary inputs:

- data/processed/external_input_surface_mapping.json

Script:

- python3 scripts/export_paper_artifacts.py

Table 2: Input-Surface to Semantic-Sink Matrix

Outputs:

- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_2_input_surface_sink_matrix.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_2_input_surface_sink_matrix.csv

Primary inputs:

- data/processed/input_surface_sink_matrix.json

Scripts:

- python3 scripts/generate_input_surface_sink_matrix.py
- python3 scripts/export_paper_artifacts.py

Table 3: Prompt Contribution by Model and Stage

Outputs:

- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_3_prompt_contribution.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_3_prompt_contribution.csv

Primary inputs:

- data/processed/runtime_phase_contributions_modelstudio_qwen3.5-plus.json
- data/processed/runtime_phase_contributions_google_gemini-3-flash.json
- data/processed/runtime_phase_contributions_modelstudio_glm-5.json
- data/processed/runtime_phase_contributions_modelstudio_kimi-k2.5.json

Script:

- python3 scripts/export_paper_artifacts.py

Figure 1: Prompt Contribution of Each Task Under Qwen3.5-Plus

Outputs:

- docs/reports/artifact_eval/figure_1_qwen_prompt_share_stacked.pdf
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/figure_1_qwen_prompt_share_stacked.png

Primary inputs:

- data/processed/runtime_task_runs_modelstudio_qwen3.5-plus/index.json
- data/processed/runtime_special_task_runs_modelstudio_qwen3.5-plus/index.json

Scripts:

- python3 scripts/plot_qwen_runtime_prompt_share.py
- python3 scripts/generate_artifact_outputs.py

Table 4: Execution-Control Contribution

Outputs:

- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_4_execution_control.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_4_execution_control.csv

Primary inputs:

- data/processed/runtime_task_runs_modelstudio_qwen3.5-plus/index.json
- data/processed/runtime_special_task_runs_modelstudio_qwen3.5-plus/index.json
- data/processed/runtime_task_runs_google_gemini-3-flash/index.json
- data/processed/runtime_special_task_runs_google_gemini-3-flash/index.json
- data/processed/runtime_task_runs_modelstudio_glm-5/index.json
- data/processed/runtime_special_task_runs_modelstudio_glm-5/index.json
- data/processed/runtime_task_runs_modelstudio_kimi-k2.5/index.json
- data/processed/runtime_special_task_runs_modelstudio_kimi-k2.5/index.json

Script:

- python3 scripts/export_paper_artifacts.py

Figure 2: Alberg Diagram for Bug-Fix Commits

Outputs:

- docs/reports/artifact_eval/figure_2_alberg_bugfix.pdf
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/figure_2_alberg_bugfix.png

Primary input:

- data/processed/input_surface_path_updates.json

Scripts:

- python3 scripts/alberg_diagram.py
- python3 scripts/generate_artifact_outputs.py

Figure 3: Alberg Diagram for Code Updates

Outputs:

- docs/reports/artifact_eval/figure_3_alberg_update.pdf
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/figure_3_alberg_update.png

Primary input:

- data/processed/input_surface_path_updates.json

Scripts:

- python3 scripts/alberg_diagram.py
- python3 scripts/generate_artifact_outputs.py

Table 5: Disclosed Vulnerabilities and Protections

Outputs:

- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_5_cves_and_protections.md
- docs/reports/artifact_eval/table_5_cves_and_protections.csv

Primary inputs:

- data/raw/openclaw_cves_full_source_single_label.csv

CSV generation source:

- ../openclaw_cves_full_source_single_label.md

Scripts:

- python3 scripts/convert_cve_markdown_to_csv.py

- `python3 scripts/export_paper_artifacts.py`

Scope of This Artifact Package

This repository snapshot is intentionally reduced to the minimum set required to reproduce the paper-facing figures and tables from the committed processed data. It does not include the full raw-experiment pipeline used during the study.

The package keeps:

- the processed inputs needed by the paper artifacts,
- the scripts that transform those inputs into paper-facing outputs, and
- the generated outputs in `docs/reports/artifact_eval`.

Recommended Workflow

For artifact evaluation, use the following command:

```
python3 scripts/generate_artifact_outputs.py
```

This command is sufficient for the current package and does not require running the original benchmark or taint experiments again.